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LONG TERM EARTH OBSERVATION MARKET DEVELOPMENT OF ENVISAT-BASED SERVICES

LINE 4: Environmental Information for Marine Operations

ENVISAT MONITORING AND FORECASTING SERVICES FOR OFFSHORE INDUSTRY (EMOFOR)

ESRIN Contract No. 15595/01/I-LG

D7: Service review report, including identification and planning of solutions for any significant discrepancies raised

D8: Example packages of EO service chain supply to Fugro GEOS

D9: Example packages of improved geo-information service from Fugro GEOS

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SERVICE REVIEW REPORT (DELIVERABLE D7)

This report gives a summary of the EMOFOR service as described in the previous documents D1, D2, D3, D4-5. It reviews the action plan service implementation and provides mitigation actions .

1. Overall EMOFOR service system with three modes

The overall objective of the EMOFOR service is to provide met-ocean information to offshore operators, with a focus on current information for deepwater operators. The service will integrate information from EO data, in situ measurements and model simulations. The EMOFOR service will consist of three service modes, each of which will be activated according to the requirements from the customers:

- Hindcast mode (met-ocean statistics from model simulations and observations: in situ and remote sensing);
- Monitoring mode (real-time or near real time data from EO and in situ measurements);
- Forecasting mode (use of forecasting models).

The main characteristics of the service modes are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of EMOFOR service modes

Service mode	Service output	Information sources	Service trials in Phase 2
Hindcast mode	Provide statistical information (space and time) about the oceanographic conditions in the selected region, especially in the exploration and design phase	Time series of in situ current meter data 3-D model simulations in hindcast Statistics on eddy-kinetic energy from altimetric data	No specific trials planned. Results from previous projects will be used in the promotion
Monitoring mode	Monitor oceanographic fields combining in situ observations and EO-data during installation and production	In situ current data from platform ADCP with real time display Eddy maps from EO data using optimal combination of altimeter, IR/Visual and SAR data	Service trials planned in Northwest Europe and Gulf of Mexico
Forecast mode	Provide forecasting of extreme events for 1 – 7 days for exploration purposes, during installation of the Blow Out Preventer (BOP) and running/retrieving the riser and production	Ocean modelling system using large-scale model nested to high-resolution regional models	Service trial planned in Gulf of Mexico

2. Data sources, processing steps and output products

The data sources, processing steps and output products of the EMOFOR service are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Overview of data sources, models, processing steps and output products. Each of the boxes contains modules for processing specific types of data and running the models required for the areas where the service will be implemented. The dashed lines indicate the current measurement service that Fugro GEOS already provides to the offshore industry.

2.1 Input data

The first category of input data to the service consists of the following satellite data: i) altimetric Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) and current products for eddy mapping and gridded SLA fields for use in modelling; ii) SAR images analysed for eddy mapping; iii) infrared images analysed for eddy mapping by contrast in sea surface temperature (SST) and composed into gridded SST fields for use in modelling, and iv) optical images analysed for eddy detection by contrast in ocean colour. The second category of input data is in situ measurements of currents by ADCP or other instruments mounted on deepwater rigs. In situ measurements are site specific data giving profiles of currents in the water column in real-time for the operators. These data are also used for validation of satellite-derived eddy maps and model simulations. Atmospheric fields are used to provide weather and wave forecasts as well as to deliver forcing fields for the ocean models. The ocean climatology data are used for tuning/validation of the ocean models.

2.2 Data processing

After reception of low level satellite data products from the data providers, geophysical parameters are retrieved (i.e. SST and SLA fields), gridded fields are derived by averaging data over time (i.e. one week), and other statistical estimates are retrieved from analysis of time series of data. Specific features such as eddies are identified and annotated in SST, ocean colour and SAR images. This processing feeds information into the monitoring mode as well as to the ocean current model simulations.

2.3 Use of modelling system

The model system consists of the large-scale Atlantic-Arctic model nested to high-resolution models covering regional seas. Other models such as tidal models and coupled ice-ocean models are also available for use in the services. The model system is based on the DIADEM/TOPAZ system, providing nesting conditions for the high resolution model in specific regions where the service will be offered to customers. Oceanographic fields from satellite data (SLA and SST) provided by CLS will be assimilated into the model system. NERSC will offer the possibility of operating the model and assimilation system in three different modes as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Modes of modelling services provided by NERSC

Hindcast mode	To offer detailed statistical information (space and time) about the oceanographic condition in the selected region.
Monitoring mode	Support the monitoring by providing analysed oceanographic fields combining EO data, in situ observations and model calculations in an optimal way using advanced assimilation
Forecast mode	Integrate the analysed field forward in time to provide a 7 day forecast

2.4 Output products from the integrated EMOFOR service

The **Monitoring Mode** is currently the most important part of the met-ocean services provided by Fugro GEOS to the offshore industry, where measurements of currents, wind, waves, etc. are carried out in real time onboard a platform. The monitoring methods include use of drifters deployed in eddies transmitting positions via ARGOS. EMOFOR will offer EO data products from several satellite systems supplementing the in situ measurement systems.

CLS will provide EO products from radar altimeters, optical and infrared radiometers by integrating data from several operating satellites. Altimeter products include sea level anomalies (SLA) as shown in Fig. 2. Infrared radiometer data are used to produce sea surface temperature (SST) maps, while ocean colour maps are produced from optical images. NERSC will provide SAR images for detection of eddies and fronts in areas where the other EO data may fail to provide reliable results. SAR is expected to be most useful in areas such as in Northwest Europe where cloud cover prevails and the eddies are too small and propagate too fast to be detected with the altimeter data.

In addition to monitoring of eddies, SLA and SST fields are also used for assimilation in the model system to improve the forecasting of the current fields

Examples of monitoring products are shown in Fig. 2.

a)

Mean Sea Level Anomalies and Geostrophic Velocities from DUACS (TP+ERS+GFO)
26-Feb-2003 (CNES day 19414)

b)

Figure 2. Eddy mapping by altimeter data showing Sea Level Anomaly and Geostrophic Current on February 26 2003 in Northwest Europe (a) and Gulf of Mexico (b). Note the difference in eddy scale and velocity between the two regions. (colour scales are not identical, whereas vector scales are identical)

Figure 3. a) Example of output from the NwagH model used in hindcast mode showing surface temperature (colour code) and current (vectors) at a given time in the Faroe-Shetland region; b) is a subset of a temperature vertical section from the Diadem3H coarse resolution model across the Iceland-Scotland ridge.

Figure 4. Example of model simulations in the Gulf of Mexico showing the Loop Currents in April at two weeks interval.

The **Hindcast Mode**, using high resolution models, is normally carried out as part of the exploration/appraisal and engineering design phases of an offshore development. The model simulations, which typically run for one to many years, provide an extensive set of data on all oceanographic variables, and statistics of these parameters can be retrieved from the model data. Example of output from hindcast modelling in the Faroe-Shetland area is shown in Fig. 3. The model data are usually compared with in situ measurements as part of the model validation. Hindcast analysis of altimeter data will also be part of the EMOFOR service, providing maps of eddy kinetic energy.

The **Forecasting Mode** is used to support operations during the exploration phase as well as the subsequent production phase to ensure safe operations and avoid dangerous situations, which can arise as result of extreme currents. A key component of the exploration drilling is the installation of the Blow Out Preventer (BOP) and running/retrieving the riser. These operations are probably the most sensitive to currents. The forecasting is presently done by assessing in situ observations combined with analysis of EO data and coarse model results by experts. In EMOFOR use of high-resolution models in forecast mode will provide a much better quantitative estimation of currents on regional scales. Example of model forecast of currents and temperature in the Gulf of Mexico is shown in Figure 4. The output products of the service are specified in Table 3

Table 3. Characteristics of the main service components

Service characteristics	Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data	Eddy statistics from altimeter hindcast data	Current statistics from model hindcast data	Forecasting with models
Main product	Maps of eddies in specific regions	Eddy kinetic energy maps: mean, seasonal, monthly	3-D current fields from model runs for a given period	Forecasted current fields: 1 – 7 days
Near real time or offline	Near real time (within 1 – 2 days)	Offline	Offline	Near real time
Use of EO data	Altimeter, SAR, infrared radiometer, optical images	Altimeter data obtained over the last 10 years	SST and SLA fields	SST and SLA fields
Which satellites	JASON, ENVISAT, NOAA, etc.	Topex/Poseidon, ERS-1/-2, GFO	Topex/Poseidon, NOAA, ERS-1/-2	JASON, ENVISAT, NOAA, etc.
Use of <i>in situ</i> current measurements	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Other input data	no	no	Atmospheric forcing fields, ocean data	Atmospheric forcing fields, ocean data
Product interval	3 – 6 days	As agreed with customer	As agreed with customer	Weekly
Product format	Maps in standard format agreed with customer	Maps in standard format agreed with customer	Plots and tabular presentations of current statistics	Plots and tabular presentations of current forecasts
Product size	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte
Transmission to customers	Attachment to e-mail	Attachment to e-mail	Attachment to e-mail	Attachment to e-mail
Service chain established	Yes by CLS for SLA, SST, OC products, by NERSC for SAR	Yes, by CLS	Yes, by NERSC	Yes, by NERSC
Areas where services will be available in 2003	Global, focus on Northwest Europe, Gulf of Mexico	Global, under satellite tracks (latitude ~±/– 75°)	Atlantic Ocean	Gulf of Mexico

3. Service Organisation

In order to deliver an integrated EMOFOR service, a clear definition of functional responsibility for the service chain elements is necessary. The role of Fugro GEOS, CLS and NERSC to provide the various elements of the service is shown in Figure 5. The service management structure is illustrated in Fig. 6 and described in Section 2 of the Revised Business Plan (D10).

Figure 5. Functional responsibilities of EMOFOR project partners

Figure 6. Management structure of the EMOFOR services where Fugro GEOS is the current sales agent. Ocean Numerics Ltd. is planned to become the sales agent as soon as the company is fully established.

Fugro GEOS will have the overall responsibility to compile, store and distribute the service products to the customers, CLS will deliver altimetric products, sea surface temperature products and ocean colour products for use in eddy mapping and for preparation of gridded data sets used for assimilation in the forecasting model. NERSC will deliver model simulations for use in hindcast analysis and in forecasting. NERSC will also deliver eddy maps from SAR when required.

4. Service levels for monitoring and forecasting

The EMOFOR monitoring and forecasting service components are classified into four levels where Level 1 provides low-cost services that are highly automated with minimum human input. The amount of data, analysis, human support and service cost increase up to Level 4. The four levels of are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4. Definition of service levels

SERVICE LEVEL	EARTH OBSERVING PRODUCTS	ANALYSIS	STANDARD CURRENT FORECAST	HIGH RESOLUTION CURRENT FORECAST
	Monitoring services		Forecasting services	
1	X			
2	X	X		
3	X	X	X	
4	X	X		X

Service Level 1 consists of weekly or bi-weekly delivery of EO based charts for a particular region of client interest. This is similar product to CLS' CATSAT service. At this level the products are developed and delivered automatically and there is no interpretation or analysis of the charts and no forecast provision. The charts would include where appropriate:

- Sea surface temperature charts
- Sea surface height charts
- Ocean colour charts
- Overlays of geostrophic current vectors (derived from sea surface heights) where possible.

Service Level 2 consists of similar products to Level 1, however the charts would be analysed and described to the Client in text. Use of SAR data will be included if necessary for eddy analysis in order to capture features that are not observable in the Level 1 products. This is similar to the EddyWatch service described in Section 5 of the Revised Business Plan (D10). The narrative would include:

- Discussion on features observed and how they relate to the situation from the previous week
- Empirical forecast of feature positions

Service Level 3 consists of the EO products as well as the results of the (coarse) Atlantic current forecast model. The results from the model would be combined with the EO products to provide a 3D nowcast as well as a forecast.

Deliverables at Service Levels 1-3 can be quickly made available for geographical regions beyond the Gulf of Mexico and a plan for wider promotion of these products is in preparation.

Service Level 4 improves on Level 3 through provision of forecast model results from the fine mesh model. The plan is to initially offer this service only in the Gulf of Mexico. Once proven in technical and commercial terms, Level 4 product generation can then be extended to other target geographical areas in the Atlantic.

5. Data Flow and Data Warehouse

The Data Warehouse will be a server located at Fugro GEOS' Swindon office. The Data Warehouse is the central node in the EMOFOR data flow as shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. EMOFOR Data Flow Diagram

The functions of the Data Warehouse are as follows:

- Structured storage of geo-referenced EO data arrays from CLS
- Structured storage of geo-referenced model ocean forecast arrays from NERSC
- Data archive of EMOFOR products

The primary purpose of the Data Warehouse will be as an operational server to receive and store incoming source data from which the EMOFOR data products will be generated for client dissemination. However, it will also act as an archive, storing consistent historical sets of EMOFOR data and data products on a weekly basis. This will be a resource from which other services may be provided subsequently (i.e. hindcast model and historical EO data).

CLS and NERSC would populate their respective secure FTP sites with the geo-referenced EO data arrays/images and model ocean forecast arrays. Data would be uploaded automatically from CLS and NERSC via secure FTP sites to Fugro GEOS. These data would then be uploaded on a regular basis, nominally weekly, for storage in the Data Warehouse. The model and satellite information would be stored in a central database of the Data Warehouse within the Fugro GEOS network. The data would therefore be subject to the provisions already in place to protect confidentiality and integrity. This includes data referencing, and rigorous back-up procedures.

For service Levels 1 and 2, the EMOFOR products are based entirely on EO data and interpretation. The information to be transferred from CLS to the Data Warehouse would comprise the following geo-referenced data arrays and JPEG images for a given region and time:

- Sea surface temperature
- Sea surface height
- Ocean colour
- Geostrophic current vectors

For service Levels 3 and 4, in addition to the above, numerical model data would be provided from the NERSC HYCOM model. It is anticipated that the transfer of forecast data on the fine grid with a 7 day horizon would comprise approximately 1.7 GByte if all model levels were provided. These data would similarly be sent by FTP to the Data Warehouse in geo-referenced data arrays. In the initial trials, we would anticipate providing only surface current velocity data. However, a future enhanced product would include forecast current velocity profile information. This would be of particular interest to drilling operations and marine construction operations.

The data would be stored in a structured database on a dedicated EMOFOR server, established within Fugro GEOS' IT infrastructure. The EMOFOR database tables would be designed, bearing on the extensive oceanographic experience of the three partner organisations.

Key database tables to include:

- Location – co-ordinates and co-ordinate system (UTM)
- Date and time – timebase (GMT)
- Elevation (reference elevation to be mean sea level)
- Parameters (temperature, colour, velocity, height etc. - units, conventions etc.)

EMOFOR data chart products would be generated routinely at Fugro GEOS, based on the geo-referenced EO and model-derived data sets in the Data Warehouse. These would be produced for the region of interest. A common mapping presentation would be adopted, showing:

- Coastline
- Bathymetry
- Offshore concessions

An example basemap is provided in Figure 8..

For service Levels 3 and 4, we would anticipate providing bespoke maps, tailored to the specific application of the client, and including representation of client area of interest (seismic shoot area, drilling location, tow transit etc.).

The final EMOFOR product would be provided as a compressed format PDF file containing the deliverables specific to the required service level. Compact size would be of particular importance for delivery to some offshore installations where data communication facility is limited.

Figure 8. Example Base Map for EMOFOR Deliverables, Showing Coastline, Bathymetry and Offshore Concessions

6. Client Interface with EMOFOR

EMOFOR would use the Internet as the principal means of service ordering and product provision as shown in Figs. 9 and 10. The advantage of an internet-based approach is that service flexibility and usability are maximised and a wide range of user requirements is catered for. There are several

means by which the service can be implemented for a given client, depending on the individual set of circumstances:

1. For multi-rig or multi-vessel operations, whilst each facility would have interest only in local conditions, a central shore-based controller could have access to all rig web-sites. In such cases, the level of service required might be defined by the operating company and the same products would be delivered to each offshore facility. Depending on company policy, either individual rigs or shore-based personnel could contact Fugro GEOS for additional service products.

This approach potentially would enable operator collectives to pool information and to observe certain dynamic features (e.g. eddies) in advance at upstream monitoring facilities. Use of encrypted data products would overcome any commercial issues of access to other parties' data.

2. Timed delivery: a standard forecast report is made available on a password-protected web site at pre-determined times or automatically provided by e-mail. For the former the user simply logs onto the site and downloads the latest report in pdf format, which is the last in a list of previous forecasts. This is the simplest delivery method, but is relatively inflexible, although a series of report options of differing levels of detail or with different emphasis could be made available. The latter style of service is currently offered by Fugro GEOS in the Trinidad Ring Advisory Co-operative (TRAC), which provides weekly updates of the movement of large eddies off the northern coast of Brazil based on altimeter data and surface drifter trajectories.
3. On demand service: on an as-required basis the user sends an email to a unique Fugro GEOS address, or telephones Fugro GEOS, giving details of the location and required information (from a pre-defined list of service options or presentations). The selected presentations are then extracted from the data warehouse and placed on the password-protected web-site or emailed back to the user. This system is currently in use by Fugro GEOS for providing members of the North West Approaches Group (NWAG) of oil companies with model data produced by NERSC. Figure 9 shows sample pages from the web-site.

Enabling a choice of presentation options would give the user a degree of control over the service for which he is paying. The level of technical detail provided would be automatically commensurate with his oceanographic knowledge. Similar systems are operated by CLS (CATSAT) and by Fugro GEOS' marine weather forecasting services (Figure 10) although with the former bespoke software is required aboard the receiving vessel to display and interact with the downloaded maps.

Fugro GEOS marine weather forecasters operate a round-the-clock service to respond to telephone and email requests for forecasts. Although a standard report is generally the default, the forecasters are able to provide a range of other, more tailored products. If the request is the first from a user, he will be given a user name and password that will enable him to log in to the web site and download his forecasts when they are ready. The forecasters offer expert technical support during critical operations, a facility that is also anticipated in the EMOFOR service.

a)

b)

Figure 9. Examples of user interface to Fugro GEOS' on-demand service: a) for ocean modelling services, and b) for NWAG (North West Approaches Group) data access.

Figure 10. Example of user interface to Fugro GEOS' marine weather forecasting services.

7. Service trials planned for 2003

7.1 Justification for the service trials

The service trials to be implemented and demonstrated in 2003 are considered to be essential for the EMOFOR service to reach the market because:

- New services need to be demonstrated and proven to key customers;
- Service trials will take place in areas of high offshore activities in deepwater;
- It is necessary to test the services in areas of different oceanographic conditions that are challenging to monitor/forecast;
- The data and model simulations from the service trials will be important for validation of the monitoring and forecasting capability;
- The service costs estimates can be verified and help to improve the business plan;
- The results from the service trials will be important in promotion and marketing.

7.2 Overview of the service trials

Two service scenarios will be implemented and demonstrated in Phase 2:

- Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data in near real time
- Forecasting using models and data assimilation

The service trials will be set up for specific regions where Fugro GEOS and the offshore industry are active and there is a potential market for the services: Gulf of Mexico and Northwest Europe (West Scotland and Shetland area). The location of the service trials are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5. Location of service trials

Service scenario	Planned areas for service trials		
	Monitoring mode (near real time)	Hindcast mode (statistics from time series)	Forecasting mode (1 – 7 days)
1 Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data	Gulf of Mexico Northwest Europe		
2 Eddy statistics from altimeter hindcast data		No specific service trial	
3 Statistics from model hindcast data		No specific service trial	
4 Forecasting using models and data assimilation			Gulf of Mexico

Customers of Fugro GEOS will be involved in the detailed planning and implementation of the service trials and for evaluation of the results of the service trials, which are planned to be completed by the end of 2003.

7.3 Eddy mapping using EO data

Areas

It is planned to carry out eddy mapping service trials in two different regions where deepwater development is ongoing and oceanographic processes and met-ocean conditions are different. This will require that the EMOFOR service can be adapted to given conditions in any ocean region.

- In Northwest Europe where the inflow of the North-Atlantic Current generates eddies along self breaks where several deep water exploration areas are under development. The eddies are frequently found in the inflow of Atlantic water through the Faroe-Shetland Channel, propagating into the Norwegian Sea. The eddies develop fairly quickly and propagate to the northeast. Due to frequent cloud cover, optical and IR images have limited usefulness, whereas altimeter and SAR can deliver more regular information.
- In the Gulf of Mexico the dominant processes of importance for deepwater operations are the Loop Current and eddies shed from it. The Loop Current eddies have long lifetime (several months) and they are shed off typically one per year. They are well suited for observations by satellite data, with altimeter derived SLA as well as optical and IR images.

Data acquisition and product preparation

The two different regions are chosen because the character of the eddies is different and the detection capability can be tested under different metocean conditions. The frequency of observation is determined by the propagation speed, which is relatively high in Northwest Europe and relatively slow in the Gulf of Mexico. For both regions, altimeter SLA maps will be produced at an interval from 2 – 7 days, depending on quickly the eddies move. Infrared and optical images from MERIS/ASAR/AATSR used in synergy with NOAA AVHRR and other satellite data will be acquired and used in near real time (i.e. within 1 day) to identify and monitor the propagation of the eddies. Under cloud free conditions IR and optical images will be used, while SAR will be used under cloudy conditions. Northwest Europe will have more cloudy days than the Gulf of Mexico, indicating that SAR data will be more useful in the former area.

Timing of service trial and involvement of customers

The eddy tracking service trials in the two regions will be carried out during a period of up to 3 months in 2003. Shell and BP who are working actively in offshore development in Northwest Europe and in Gulf of Mexico will be involved in the planning and implementation of the service trials as receivers of the products to be delivered. The timing of the service trials will be done in agreement with Shell and BP. In Northwest Europe the service trial will be relatively short, about 4 weeks with intense, daily delivery of products to a selected customer. In the Gulf of Mexico, where eddy life time is longer and advection is slower compared to Northwest Europe, the service trial will last for several months and with delivery of EO products tentatively once per week.

The first test image from ASAR over the trial area west of Shetland/Scotland is shown in Fig. 11. The image was delivered by KSAT (Kongsberg Satellite Services, former Tromsø Satellite Station) in near real time for testing data ordering and acquisition.

a

Figure 11. a) ENVISAT ASAR wide-swath image over the Faroe-Scotland region obtained on 17 January 2003. The Schiehallion FPSO is indicated by the arrow at position 60°21'N 004°04'W. The image is dominated by wind gusts including convection cells and rain showers. These features mask any currents, fronts or eddy signatures. Eddy mapping by SAR requires lower wind speeds.

b) Bathymetric map of the Faroe-Scotland region with the main currents. The Schiehallion FPSO site is indicated by the arrow

b

c	d
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Figure 12. Weekly maps of Mean Sea Level Anomaly and Geostrophic Velocities from altimeter in the Faroe-Shetland area for February 2003 provided by CLS.

7.4 Forecasting in the Gulf of Mexico

In the Gulf of Mexico the position of the Loop Current and its eddies, which represent the maximum currents, need to be monitored and forecasted for deepwater operations. The forecasting service trial will be co-ordinated with eddy mapping using EO data. The main deep water concessions where forecasting of loop currents is required are the Mississippi Canyon, Green Canyon and Garden Banks (Fig. 13)

Figure 13. Deep water concessions in the Gulf of Mexico. The arrows indicate the key areas for service trial validation.

The pre-operational ocean monitoring and forecasting system at NERSC consists of a physical ocean model (HYCOM), which is coupled to a dynamic and thermodynamic sea-ice model, and a

marine ecosystem model. This system, which is presently running in real time for the North Atlantic within the EU-funded DIADEM and TOPAZ projects, is forced using atmospheric data obtained from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast (ECMWF). Sea Surface Temperature (SST) and Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) data from satellites are assimilated weekly using the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF). This system is under development to provide two types of services for the offshore industry: 1) hindcast simulations; and 2) forecasting of oceanographic variables (current, temperature, salinity, etc.). The hindcast data from every model grid point is used to calculate statistics of currents. This is then compared with statistics from current measurements. Model simulations used in combination with observed current data is a cost-effective tool for estimation of extreme criteria for deep water construction. Forecasting is provided by the same model system when run in real time using the assimilation of weekly SST and SLA fields and forced by forecast atmospheric fields.

The GOM forecasting service is co-ordinated with the TOPAZ project which has funded the development of a high resolution operational model for the Gulf of Mexico. The TOPAZ system, using an operational model for the Atlantic and Arctic basins will provide boundary conditions. This model has a 30 km resolution in the Gulf of Mexico which seems too coarse for a good representation of some important processes in this region (dynamics inside channels, dynamics of the loop current and vortices, river plumes, etc.).

The resolution has been increased to about 5 km for the regional GOM model. Free run (without any correction from data assimilation) results are currently analysed. Qualitatively, the GOM model shows much better dynamical properties for the currents in the Yucatan channel including a better return current, and of course for small scale processes such as development of small scale meanders along fronts, etc. Quantitative analysis must however be made before assessing the general model quality.

In parallel, a data assimilation system has been developed for the GOM model. It is based on the EnOI system developed at NERSC (Ensemble Optimal Interpolation) which works exactly as the EnKF system except for the choice of a static ensemble which is now sampled from a free run model simulation over a selected time period (the EnKF uses "statistically perturbed" model states which evolves in time according to the model dynamics).

The service trial will be carried out over several months of 2003. System start-up date is estimated to be 1. May, and forecasting will start to be produced from about 1. June. The forecast will be carried out for 7 days and be repeated at the same interval. Altimetric MSLA and SST products will be used for assimilation. Shell and BP as key customers will be involved in the planning and implementation of the service trials.

7.5 Validation

Remote sensing validation

Intercomparison of eddy mapping from different EO sensors (i.e. altimeter, infrared/optical images and SAR) will be carried out as the primary validation method as part of the service trials. Eddy maps will be quality controlled by such intercomparison before products are distributed to the customer. In addition, surface current maps produced by EO data will be validated against *in situ* current measurements obtained at platforms operated by Shell/BP in the areas where the test trials will take place. This will be done after the trials when *in situ* data becomes available. Examples of EO products in the Gulf of Mexico are shown in Fig. 14.

Model validation

The ocean modelling and data assimilation system is undergoing continuous online verification and validation. During the implementation phase, before start of the test trial, it is verified that the system represents the characteristics of water masses correctly and in addition reproduces the known physical processes in the region of interest. This has in some cases involved the tuning of some model parameters to ensure that the variability and energetics of the model is as close as possible to what is observed.

Figure 14. Simultaneous EO products from different sensors in the Gulf of Mexico: a) SST map in from 10 February 2003, and b) MSLA and geostrophic velocity from 12 February 2003.

Some preliminary tests are currently done (Fig. 15). The data that are assimilated for these tests are coarse Reynolds SST data. They are smooth and do not induce strong corrections on the small scales. These preliminary tests have underlined the link between the observations and the chosen ensemble, and a detailed analysis has been undertaken to understand this link. We expect this will lead to the definition of a procedure to optimize the performances of the EnOI filter for the GOM application and real time assimilation of both high resolution SST and SLA data. In addition we will later assimilate in situ profiles of temperature and salinity from the ARGO program.

Figure 15. Example of model simulation of SST in the Gulf of Mexico using the TOPAZ system.

During the service trial, when the system is run operationally or in forecasting mode, the model predictions are compared with the data which are assimilated and the statistics of these differences

are computed to identify eventual biases or systematic errors. The variance of these differences is also used to verify that the prescribed statistical model and data errors are as realistic as possible.

Additional independent data such as current meter moorings will be used for intercomparison with the model outputs when they are available after the test trial. The current meter data provides an additional measure of the model forecast quality.

8. Review of action plan and mitigation measures

8.1 Cost of services

The cost of services is estimated and reported in D10 Consolidated Business Plan. The cost estimates will be verified through the service trials in WP4000. The cost elements and financing will be re-analysed as part of the refined business plan. When the market review is going to be performed cost versus benefit of the service modes will be assessed based on feedback from the strategic customers.

8.2 Access and cost of EO data

Data from ENVISAT such as RA-2, MERIS and AATSR are not yet available for near real time use. Therefore, CLS are using other existing satellites systems and remote sensing instruments that are fully operational for the service until the ENVISAT data are ready. ASAR data can be delivered from KSAT in Norway for the test trial in West Shetland/Scotland region. The commercial price for ENVISAT data, is now established. RA-2, MERIS and AATSR will be available at reproduction cost, and will therefore not have any significant impact on the service cost. The commercial price of SAR images to be used in eddy tracking represent the largest cost factor of EO data for the eddy tracking service. Commercial price for RADARSAT data is 3000 USD per ScanSAR scene, while preliminary price of ENVISAT ASAR Wideswath scene is 1500 Euro. The service trials and the market assessment will be used to assess if and under what conditions SAR data are cost-effective for the customers. Use of SAR data will be balanced against use of less expensive altimetry and optical/IR images. Eddy mapping will be based on four types of EO-data products: altimetry, infrared images, optical images and SAR images. This gives good backup in case one or two of the products are not available or useful.

8.3 Involvement of a key customer in the service trials

Fugro GEOS has selected Shell and BP as the key customers for each of the two areas where the service trials are planned (WP4000). In the Gulf of Mexico (GOM) Shell will be the key customer, while in Northwest Europe/West Scotland (WoS) it will be BP. The key customers will participate in the planning and implementation of the service trials, including definition of the products, contents and layout of the products, timing and delivery, etc. In situ data will be provided by the key customers for validation of the EO-data as well as the model simulations. The key customers

will provide comments and feedback to the services and make recommendation for improvements.

8.4 Clarification of limitations and advantages of the proposed EO-based products

All information sources on metocean conditions have technical advantages as well as disadvantages. EO data has a unique advantage compared to other observing systems in the synoptic mapping of large ocean surface areas. The mapping capability for eddies is limited in various ways for the different sensors. The service trials will be used to clarify the limitations as well as advantages of EO-based products in two service trial regions (WP4000). For validation of SAR eddy mapping in WoS, archived SAR data will be used. During the operational service trial, near real time ASAR data from KSAT will be used. The altimeter products as well as the IR and optical products from CLS will be validated for the West Scotland area as well as for the GOM. The outcome of the validation of the EO data will be used to make recommendations for improvements of the EO-products (WP5000) in order to expand the service into larger markets (WP6000)

8.5 Validation of the HYCOM model in GOM

WP4000 will contain significant validation activities for the HYCOM model results in GOM as part of the service trials, because eddy forecasting is very critical and a successful service depends on trust in the model performance. The validation will show if there is a need for further testing and tuning of the model before a commercial service can start during 2004. Meteorological forcing data will be assessed as well. Further validation and assessment of the HYCOM model will be done as part of the consolidation in WP5000 before the model is published as part of the service.

8.6 Define the end product that will be distributed to customers

After products from CLS and NERSC are delivered to FG, a qualified person at FG will extract the most important information from the products and compile a map with simple presentation and explanatory text that will be sent to the end user working on a platform. The first weeks of the service trials will be used to define the format and contents of end products (WP4000).

8.7 Delivery of products from NERSC and CLS to FG Data Warehouse

During the trials products from CLS and NERSC will be delivered to the FG Data Warehouse by ftp or e-mail attachment at agreed times. For GOM, the products will be delivered weekly, whereas for WoS the delivery will be twice per week. FG will then compile a simple end-user product and send to Shell and BP as e-mail attachments. The Data Warehouse will store all incoming products from NERSC and CLS as well as various data products from FG end products for customers.

8.8 Assessment of service trials

The service trials will be important to assess the role of EO data and the HYCOM model as part of a met-ocean monitoring and forecasting service. After the service trials have been completed and their cost estimates re-analysed, a market assessment will be performed based on the technical quality and cost of the service (WP4000). This will be used in assessment of further service viability.

8.9 Preparation and start-up of commercial service

During the service trials the business plan for the services will be updated. Agreement between the FG, NERSC and CLS will be made concerning costs and revenues. Ocean Numerics will be staffed and involved as the company that will run the commercial services. The service will be announced publicly and marketing efforts will be made to reach the main market as describe din the business plan.

8.10 Further marketing and promotion activities

A plan for wider marketing and promotion activities will be prepared by Fugro GEOS as part of WP6000 and WP7000, taking into account that the market is very competitive and correct timing and contents of the marketing efforts will be essential for further development of the service. Fugro GEOS' global network and regional offices will be used for these activities.

8.11. Documentation of product quality

The single most important factor to succeed in the market is to offer high quality products. The quality of the products can best be documented through an extensive validation process where systematic comparison is done against in situ data. Such validation is going on as part of other projects (i.e. TOPAZ) and will be used as background for the forecasting service.

8.12 Throughput capacity and capacity to reach a global market

The throughput capacity is not considered to be a bottleneck in the service delivery at the present stage. The personnel and computer resources at NERSC/CLS and Fugro GEOS can easily produce and deliver the products proposed for the geographical areas described in the business plan. For EO data CLS already provides global service by the CATSAT so extension to a global market has been done. For modelling services, NERSC has built modelling capacity for the Atlantic Ocean and the surrounding seas. Extension to other oceans will require further testing and validation.

**EXAMPLES OF EO SERVICE CHAIN SUPPLY FROM NERSC AND CLS
TO FUGRO GEOS (DELIVERABLE D8)**

and

**IMPROVED GEO-INFORMATION SERVICE FROM FUGRO GEOS
(DELIVERABLE D9)**

The attached fact sheets describes the geo-information services to be provided.